
**EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF JOB SATISFACTION AND ORGANIZATIONAL
COMMITMENT AMONG ACADEMIC STAFF IN POLYTECHNIC SYSTEM**

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Abstract

The study examined Job Satisfaction and Organisational Commitment among academic staff in Polytechnic system. The Job Satisfaction constructs would examine payment of salary, promotion and working condition while Organisational Commitment will be measured along three dimensions namely: affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment. Survey research design will be adopted for the study through the use of questionnaire. The population of the study comprises all academics (lecturers) in Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi while a sample of 254 was statistically selected using Yamane's formula. Based on this, a structured questionnaire was designed and administered to elicit information from respondents. 133 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and used for statistical analyses. Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, correlation and regression analyses were utilized as statistical tools to analyse the research data using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.0. The study revealed that job satisfaction constructs such as promotion and working conditions have a positive and significant relationship with organisational commitment. The study, therefore, recommends that for management to get lecturers committed to teaching and research, they must be promoted as at when due with the accompanying financial benefits. The promotion process must be transparent, fair and free from nepotism and godfatherism.

Keywords: Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Empirical, Staff, Polytechnic System
